

Studies on the Citrate Complex of Nickel by Solubility, pH-titration, and Conductometric Titration Methods

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Citrate complex of nickel has been studied by solubility, conductometric and pH, titration methods. In the case of solubility in 25% neutralised citric acid, the equilibrium constant is found to be 6.838×10^6 and that in 50%, 75%, and 100% neutralised citric acid is 1.62×10^3 .

The neutral complex (C), formed at a lower pH, containing one citrate ligand per g. of Ni, dissociates like dibasic acid to anionic complexes (C_1^- and C_2^{2-}). The existence of the complexes has been confirmed by pH titration and conductometric methods.

Nickel citrate complex has already been studied by the authors' by pH-titration methods. The investigation has been carried out by the solubility of nickel hydroxide in partially neutralised citric acid. In case of the solubility in 25% neutralised citric acid, the equilibrium constant of the reaction:

is found to be 6.838×10^6 . In the case of solubility in 50%, 75%, and 100% neutralised citric acids, the equilibrium constant of the reaction:

is found to be 1.62×10^3 . The equilibrium constant of the reaction:

is found to be 1.28×10^{-9} .

The neutral complex (C), which is formed at a lower pH, containing one citrate ligand per g. atom of nickel, dissociates like a dibasic acid to anionic complexes (C_1^- and C_2^{2-}). The existence of the complexes C, C_1^- , and C_2^{2-} has been confirmed by pH-titration and conductometric titration methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel (II) hydroxide was prepared by very gradual addition of a dilute solution of NaOH from a dropping funnel to a solution of nickel nitrate under mechanical stirring. The addition of alkali was stopped when the solution became just alkaline. The precipitate was allowed to settle and the supernatant liquid decanted. The precipitate was washed with hot water several times with decantation and finally filtered by suction. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with hot water till free of alkali and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. The nickel content of the dry sample was estimated by dimethylglyoxime. The sample was found to contain 63.20% Ni, whereas Ni(OH)_2 contains 63.33% of Ni. In the study of the

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1. This *Journal*, 1957, 34, 619.

solubility of nickel hydroxide in partially neutralised citric acid, nickel was estimated as dimethylglyoxime complex. By addition of different amounts of citric acid to a fixed amount of nickel sulphate and subsequent estimation of nickel content, it has been concluded that citric acid has no effect in the estimation of nickel by dimethylglyoxime method.

Determination of Solubility of Ni(OH)₂ in Partially Neutralised Citric Acid

A citric acid solution (0.5*M*) was prepared and standardised. Calculated amount of this citric acid (which on dilution to one litre would provide 0.1*M* citric acid) was taken in four conical flasks (750-ml capacity) and the calculated amount of *N*-NaOH was added to the solution in conical flasks to neutralise 25% of citric acid in the first, 50% of the citric acid in the second, 75% of the citric acid in the third, and 100% in the fourth flask. Excess of nickel hydroxide, prepared above, was added and the mixture refluxed for 3-4 days over a water bath. Then the solutions were allowed to cool inside the thermostat, maintained at 35°. Finally the solutions were filtered separately into one-litre measuring flasks. The washings of the conical flask and the residual nickel hydroxide were collected in the measuring flask. The solutions were diluted to one litre.

The solutions were then diluted to various extents, so that the total citrate concentrations would be 0.1*M*, 0.08*M*, 0.07*M*, 0.05*M*, 0.04*M*, and 0.02*M*, respectively, and were taken in glass-stoppered bottles. Solid nickel hydroxide, prepared above, was added and the bottles with contents were heated for 1 hr. on a water bath, maintained at about 50-60°. These were then placed in an air thermostat at 35° for two weeks to attain equilibrium. The solutions were then filtered and analysed for nickel contents as dimethylglyoxime complex. The pHs of the solutions were measured. The results obtained with 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% neutralised acids are recorded in Tables I—IV, respectively.

TABLE I

[Cit].	pH.	† Ni-complex formed.	**[C ₁ -].	[H ₂ Cit ⁻] × 109.	K ₁ * × 10 ⁻⁶ .
0.10 <i>M</i>	7.55	0.2816 g.	0.09747	15.110	6.449
0.08	7.57	0.2251	0.07793	11.280	6.908
0.07	7.60	0.1970	0.06821	8.506	8.021
0.05	7.62	0.1402	0.04853	6.666	7.623
0.04	7.74	0.1100	0.03808	4.795	7.941
0.02	7.83	0.0503	0.01742	4.260	4.089

† Expressed in g./10ml of soln.

** Expressed in g. atom of Ni.

Nickel hydroxide is almost insoluble in water; the solubility product is about 10⁻¹⁸, which means that the saturated solution is about 10⁶ normal (about 0.1 mg./litre)².

The solubility product of nickel hydroxide is of the order 10⁻¹⁸. Hence the solubility of nickel hydroxide at pH 7.55 (the lowest pH in the 25% neutralised system) and 9.4 (the highest pH in the 100% neutralised system) would be of the order of 1.8 × 10⁻⁶ and 3.6 × 10⁻¹⁰ g. moles, respectively. The solubility in partially neutralised citric acid is much higher and the above may be neglected. The whole of nickel is assumed to be present as complex.

In Fig. 1, total nickel in the solution containing 0.1 M total citrate was plotted against

FIG. 1

HCit²⁻ ion. The curve rises in the beginning from the 25% neutralised citric acid and reaches maximum at 50% neutralised citric acid; it then falls gradually at 75% neutralisation series, and finally attains the minimum at the 100% neutralisation of citric acid. This indicates that the solubility, *i.e.*, the formation of the complex, depends on the concentration of the monohydrogen citrate ion.

The concentrations of H₂Cit⁻, HCit²⁻, and Cit³⁻ ions were obtained as follows:

Total citrate = free citrate + citrate in the complex.

Total citrate = [Ct].

Citrate in the complex = total nickel = [Ni].

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\text{Ct}] - [\text{Ni}] &= [\text{H}_3\text{Cit}] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] + [\text{Cit}^{3-}] \\
 &= \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1} \cdot [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]} [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + \frac{k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^2} [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] \\
 [\text{Ct}] - [\text{Ni}] &= [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1} + 1 + \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right) \quad \dots (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

[Ct], [Ni], [H⁺], *k*₁, *k*₂, and *k*₃ are known.

Hence [H₂Cit⁻] can be calculated according to equation (1). [HCit²⁻] and [Cit³⁻] can be calculated from the value of [H₂Cit⁻].

In 50%, 75%, and 100% neutralised series, the solubility is found to depend on the concentration of HCit²⁻. It is therefore very probable that nickel hydroxide reacts with HCit²⁻ in these series, whereas in 25% neutralised series, the reaction takes place with H₂Cit⁻ ions which are comparatively in high concentration. The reactions do not result in the liberation of protons as the *pH* of the solutions is not lowered. Hence the reaction in 25% neutralised series and the equilibrium constant may be represented by equation (2) and (2-1), respectively.

$$\frac{[\text{C}_1^-]}{[\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-]} = K_1^* \quad \dots (2-1)$$

[C₁⁻] = [Ni]. [H₂Cit⁻] has been calculated as discussed above. *K*₁^{*} has been calculated by equation (2-1) providing values recorded in Table II.

The mean value of K_1^* is 6.838×10^6 .

The reactions in 50%, 75%, and 100% neutralised series is assumed to be

The equilibrium constant of the reaction is given by

$$\frac{[\text{C}_2^{2-}]}{[\text{HCit}^{2-}]} = K_2^*$$

$[\text{C}_2^{2-}] = [\text{Ni}]$. $[\text{H.Cit}^{1-}]$ was calculated from (H_2Cit^-) obtained by equation (1). The values of K_2^* thus calculated are shown in Tables II, III, and IV, respectively, for 50%, 75%, and 100% neutralised series. K_2^* obtained from 50% and 75% neutralised series agree fairly well.

TABLE II

[Cit].	pH.	†Ni-complex formed.	**[C ₂ ²⁻].	[HCit ²⁻] × 10 ⁵ .	K ₂ [*] × 10 ⁻³ .
0.10M	8.40	0.1788 g.	0.06190	4.677	1.323
0.08	8.34	0.1728	0.05981	2.847	2.101
0.07	8.40	0.1396	0.04833	2.664	1.814
0.05	8.68	0.0872	0.03018	1.276	2.365
0.04	8.58	0.0752	0.02603	1.128	2.308
0.02	8.70	0.3540	0.12260	0.474	2.587

TABLE III

[Cit].	pH.	*Ni-complex formed.	**[C ₂ ²⁻].	[HCit ²⁻] × 10 ⁵ .	K ₂ [*] × 10 ⁻³ .
0.10M	9.08	0.1260 g.	0.04362	1.4470	3.013
0.08	8.90	0.0852	0.02949	1.9620	1.503
0.07	8.84	0.0708	0.02451	2.0290	1.200
0.05	8.91	0.0496	0.01717	1.2460	1.379
0.04	8.95	0.0434	0.01503	0.8622	1.744
0.02	8.92	0.6286	0.00990	0.3745	2.643

TABLE IV

[Cit].	pH.	†Ni-complex formed.	**[C ₂ ²⁻].	[HCit ²⁻] × 10 ⁵ .	K ₂ [*] × 10 ⁻³ .
0.10M	9.44	0.01390 g.	0.0019250	11.000	1.751
0.08	9.42	0.01112	0.0015400	9.212	1.671
0.07	9.40	0.00980	0.0013570	8.429	1.610
0.05	9.39	0.00888	0.0009528	6.162	1.546
0.04	9.16	0.00640	0.0008863	8.351	1.061
0.02	9.14	0.00320	0.0004431	4.383	1.011

(The mean values of K_2^* in 50% and 75% neutralised series are 1.92×10^3 and 1.33×10^3 respectively). The mean value of K_2^* in 100% neutralised series is 1.44×10^2 which is less by a factor of 10. This is difficult to explain. Some other reaction might be taking place

* Expressed in g./10 ml soln.

** Expressed in g. atom of Ni.

at this pH in 100% neutralised series. The value of K_2^* is therefore taken as the average value of K_2^* obtained in 50% and 75% neutralised series (1.62×10^3).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{K_2^*}{K_1^*} &= \frac{[C_2^{2-}]}{[C_1^-]} \times \frac{[H_2 \text{ Cit}^-]}{[H \text{ Cit}^{2-}]} \\ &= \frac{[C_2^{2-}]}{[C_1^-]} \times \frac{[H^+][\text{HCit}^{2-}]}{[\text{HCit}^{2-}]} \\ \frac{K_2^* \times k_2}{K_1^*} &= \frac{[C_2^{2-}][H^+]}{[C_1^-]} = K_2 \quad \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

The value of K_2 obtained by substitution of the values of K_2^* , K_1^* and k_2 in equation (4) is 1.28×10^{-6} , whereas the value obtained from pH-titration method¹ is 1.35×10^{-6} . These two values, obtained by entirely different methods, agree fairly well.

Conductometric Titrations

Curve A (Fig. 2) represents the results of conductance titration of 260 ml of a solution containing 0.00033 g. mole of citric acid and curve B, that of the same volume of another solution containing 0.00033 g. mole of citric acid and 0.00025 g. mole of nickel sulphate against 0.1N-NaOH at 32.5°.

0.1M-NaOH added in ml.

FIG. 2

The nature of the curves A and B are similar to those obtained in the case of cobalt-citrate systems³. A break in the curve B, similar to that in the curve A at the neutralisation point, comes much later, indicating the former system to contain more acid.

A neutral complex C is formed in the beginning which does not contribute to the conductance of the solution. The neutral complex then dissociates like a dibasic acid to

complex C_1^- and C_2^{2-} . The formation of these complexes is indicated by the breaks at P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 respectively.

FIG. 3

Curve A (Fig. 3) represents the results of conductance titration of 270 ml of conductivity water and curve B, that of the same volume of another solution containing 0.001 g. mole of nickel sulphate against 0.1 *M* sodium citrate at 32°.

The nature of the curves are similar to those obtained in the investigation of cobalt-citrate complexes. Hence, the formation of a 1:1 complex is indicated here also.

The authors are grateful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research for awarding a grant for chemicals and apparatus.